

**TREATMENT OF HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE IN ELDERLY PATIENTS
WITH CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE****Mirzaeva Gulchexra Payzullayevna****Nazarova Nigina Otabekovna****Rakhimova Gulsum Polatboyevna****Xasanova Malika Akramovna**

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Introduction: Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEIs) and angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs), which have nephroprotective effects, are first-line drugs (FL) for treatment of arterial hypertension (AH) in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). However, these groups of drugs have a number of contraindications, certain adverse drug reactions, unwanted drug interactions and therefore cannot be prescribed in all AH patients with CKD. Therefore, real clinical practice studies are needed to assess the real frequency of nephroprotective drugs prescription, especially in the elderly.

Methods: We analyzed 75 case histories of elderly patients treated in the nephrology department of the 3-clinic of the Tashkent medical academy. The average duration of hospitalization was $12,79 \pm 0,26$ days. The mean age of patients was $66,24 \pm 0,56$ years (60% - women). AH of the 1st degree was revealed in 4% of patients, AH of the 2nd degree - in 36%, AH of the 3rd degree - in 60%. Stage II CKD had 2.7% of patients, stage III CKD - 61.3%, stage IV CKD - 28%, stage V CKD - 8%. Proteinuria less than 300 mg/day was detected in 24% of patients, proteinuria 300-3000 mg/day in 32%, and proteinuria over 3000 mg/day in 5.3%. Pharmacotherapy was analyzed by prescription sheets. Results: Combined antihypertensive therapy was administered in 97.3% of patients. The average number of simultaneously prescribed antihypertensive drugs per patient was 3.12 ± 0.14 . Beta-adrenoblockers (BABs) were given to 70.7% of the patients (of which bisoprolol in 58.5% of cases, metoprolol in 32.1%, nebivolol in 5.7%, atenolol in 3.8%, and carvedilol in 3.8%). Calcium antagonists (CA) were administered in 69.3% of patients (including amlodipine in 76.9%, nifedipine in extended forms in 14.7%). Diuretics (D) were received orally by 65.3% of patients (indapamide - 71.4%, furosemide - 22.4%, thorasemide - 18.4%, spironolactone - 6.1%). In addition, 14.7% of patients received intravenous furosemide. ARBs were prescribed in 45.3% of patients (fosinopril - 61.8%, enalapril - 41.2%). Centrally acting drugs were received by 25.3% of patients (rilmenidine - 68.4%, moxonidine - 38.5%). ARBs were received by

26.7% of patients (losartan - 90%, telmisartan - 5%, eprosartan - 5%). 6.7% of patients received the alpha-adrenoblocker doxazosin. In 18 cases, when ACEIs were not used, ARBs were prescribed. Thus, the total number of patients who received nephroprotective drugs (ACEIs and BRA) was 69.3%. The incidence of hyperkalemia was 39.1% and the incidence of stage V CKD was 34.8% in the group of patients who received neither (ACEIs) nor ARBs. During the performed therapy, blood pressure (BP) significantly decreased from $157.79 \pm 3.02 / 92.27 \pm 1.18$ to $128.47 \pm 1.07 / 82.33 \pm 0.83$ mm Hg. Target BP (target BP (<140/80 mm Hg) at the time of discharge was achieved in 53.3% of patients. Conclusion: The majority of elderly patients with CKD and AH received nephroprotective drugs (ACEIs and ARBs), which is in line with the current recommendations. In 30.7% of patients they were not prescribed, apparently due to hyperkalemia and the presence of marked azotemia.

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